

Studies on Bergman cyclization, the chemistry at the heart of enediynes[†]

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The kinetics of Bergman cyclization (BC) which is dependent upon a number of steric and stereoelectronic parameters, have been studied in various nitrogen-substituted cyclic enediynes. The simplest of these, a 10-membered enediyne **33** cyclized spontaneously ($t_{1/2} = 72$ h at 23°) and caused significant cleavage of supercoiled double stranded DNA at micromolar level. The degree of pyramidalization of the ring nitrogen in these enediynes has an inverse effect on the rate of cyclization. Replacement of the ene part with an aromatic ring led to a considerable elevation of activation energy for BC.

In the early 1970's, Bergman and coworkers¹ postulated that *cis*-hex-3-ene-1,5-diyne (**1**) upon thermolysis, would undergo a rearrangement to a reactive intermediate 1,4-dehydrobenzene diradical (**2**) which could then collapse either to the starting material or to the rearrangement product (**3**); alternatively, in the presence of a suitable radical donor, benzenoid product (**4**) may be obtained (Scheme 1). In natural enediynes, this cycloaromatization process, now popularly known as Bergman Cyclization, is precisely the reaction that nature employs to inflict the lethal blow to the DNA.

Scheme 1

Although Bergman cyclization is known for more than two decades, it is only from late 1980s that it has attracted considerable attention after the discovery of DNA damaging activity of natural enediynes. In their quest to design novel mimics of natural enediynes, chemists have tried to determine the factors controlling the rate of Bergman cyclization and achieved considerable progress within a short span. Usually acyclic enediynes cyclize at a high temperature (~200°); interestingly, the natural enediynes undergo the same reaction at a temperature as low as 37° (the biological temperature). To ascertain what exactly prompted

these molecules to readily undergo Bergman cyclization, studies were undertaken in various laboratories leading to the development of several theories. These are briefly described here.

In 1988, Nicolaou *et al.*² put forward a hypothesis which stated that the rate of Bergman cyclization mainly depends upon the distance between the reacting acetylenic carbons *a,b*. They prepared several simple, relatively strain-free enediyne systems and investigated their thermal stability. From MM2 calculations as well as X-ray data on various enediynes and by comparing the observed reactivities of these compounds, they concluded that in order to have spontaneous cyclization at ambient temperature, the *a,b*-distance should be in the range 3.20–3.31 Å. Molecules with *a,b*-distance lower than 3.20 Å have been claimed as transient intermediates suffering spontaneous cyclization to benzenoid systems. On the other hand, numerous examples of systems with *a,b*-distance greater than 3.31 Å are known and they are quite stable at 37°. In most of the natural enediynes, the *a,b*-distance is greater than 3.31 Å which explains their stability under ordinary conditions. However, under biological conditions, a triggering reaction takes place which lowers the *a,b*-distance below 3.31 Å, thus forcing spontaneous Bergman cyclization. The sequence of reactions is shown for calicheamicin γ_1^1 (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

[†] Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

Recently, Schreiner³ using the Density Functional Theory (DFT) estimated the activation enthalpies for the Bergman cyclization of a series of cyclic hydrocarbon enediyne and extended the 'critical range' of 3.31–3.20 Å for spontaneous cyclization to 3.4–2.90 Å.

Magnus and Fairhurst⁴, through both qualitative and quantitative experiments, and Snyder⁵, using *ab initio* methods, suggested independently that the critical factor that determines the reactivity of strained enediyne is not the a,b-distance but the difference in strain energy between the enediyne and the transition state leading to the biradical intermediate. Magnus and Fairhurst⁴ observed dramatic difference in the rates of cyclization of substrates **7** and **9** although the a,b-distances in both the molecules are virtually identical (3.4 Å) (Scheme 3). Other examples are also known

Scheme 3

where an enediyne **11** with a greater a,b-distance undergoes faster cyclization compared to **13** with a smaller a,b-distance (Scheme 4). These results seem to contradict Nicolaou's distance theory. In an attempt to explain all the observations, Snyder⁵ put forward a hypothesis which considers the difference in strain energy between the enediyne and the product-like transition state for cycloaromatization as the sole determining factor for the ring closure tendency.

Various research groups have observed the dependence of Bergman cyclization on factors based on steric or stereoelectronic grounds. For example, König *et al.*⁷ reported that the rate of Bergman cyclization depends on the conformational change in the enediyne prodrug that increases the strain of the unsaturated cyclic moiety or lower the energy of the transition state for the cyclization. This, in turn, can cause activation at the molecular level. The differential scan-

Scheme 4

ning calorimetry (DSC) of 2,2-bipyridine macrocyclic enediyne (**15**) (Scheme 5) shows an exothermic reaction at 510 K. Without metal ion coordination, the molecule exists in the less strained transoid orientation. However, coordination to the metal ion induces a change in conformation of the 2,2-bipyridine unit to a predominantly cisoid orienta-

Scheme 5

tion. In this conformation the macrocyclic enediyne is more strained, which is reflected in a decrease of the cyclization temperature to 418 K as shown by DSC.

König and Rutters⁸ also investigated whether the reactivity of a simple acyclic enediyne functionality can be modified by changing the conformation due to complexation of adjacent crown ether moieties with different metal ions (Scheme 6). DSC measurements show that Bergman cyclization begins at 415 K for **17**, at 430 K for **18** and at 442 K for **19**. The parent crown ether compounds undergo an exothermic reaction at a lower temperature compared to the enediyne complexed to metal ions. A rationale for the increased thermal stability of the metal complexes was put forward based on the electrostatic repulsion of the sodium ions in **18** and the intercalation of the large potassium ion in **19**, thus reducing the proximity of the triple bonds for cyclization.

Semmelhack *et al.*⁹ observed a decrease in the rate of cycloaromatization when the ene unit is the part of an aromatic ring. However, the placement of a quinone unit

Scheme 6

brought back the reactivity (Scheme 7). Other studies by Singh and Just¹⁰ and Nicolaou *et al.*¹¹ also suggested qualitatively the same features for aromatic enediyne systems.

Scheme 7

On the contrary, when the ene part belongs to a nitrogen heterocycle, the BC is accelerated. Thus the pyrimidine enediyne **24** was found to have an activation energy of only 16.1 kcal mol⁻¹. Cyclization of the closest aromatic analog 1,2-diethynylbenzene has an activation energy of 25.1 kcal mol⁻¹.

Scheme 8

Scheme 9

Recently, interesting studies have been carried out on acyclic enediyne where one of the unsaturated carbons is replaced by nitrogen. Kerwin and David¹² studied a potential aza-Bergman route to 2,5-didehydropyridine via the thermal rearrangement of C,N-dialkynylimines (**26**). However, these imines, when subjected to reflux conditions in benzene, rearranged to the nitrile (**28**). All attempts to trap the putative 2,5-didehydropyridine biradical failed until more recently Chen *et al.*¹³ successfully trapped the biradical employing acidic conditions (HBF₄). Presumably in the pyridine biradical, the interaction of the nitrogen lone-pair with the singlet biradical increases the singlet-triplet splitting. As a consequence the rate of H-abstraction becomes slow. The effect is reversed when the nitrogen is protonated.

For the past few years, we have been trying to understand the effect of incorporation of one or more nitrogen atoms in the enediyne framework. Our aim was to replace the saturated carbons of the backbone with nitrogen while keeping the enediyne system intact. Understanding the reactivity of the so called aza-enediyne system will help us in ultimately making better designed enediyne systems with efficient triggering devices that may be suitable for cancer chemotherapy or as tools in molecular biology.

To fulfil our objectives we decided to synthesize the 10-membered enediyne **33-35**.

Results and Discussion

Incorporation of one or more nitrogen atoms in the enediyne cyclic framework may offer certain advantages : (1) the shorter C–N bond distance may enhance the rate of BC by lowering the a,b-distance, (2) attachment of DNA-philic ligands should boost up the cleavage, (3) ligation to metal ions may speed up the kinetics of BC and (4) the possible perturbation of the kinetics of BC by changing the extent of pyramidalization of the nitrogen.

MM2 calculations on the enediyne **33** and the corresponding aromatic analog **34** revealed the a,b-distances to be 3.22 and 3.24 Å, respectively. Their energy-minimized

conformations are shown in Fig. 1.

Zerovalent Pd-catalyzed Sonogashira coupling¹⁴ is the

Fig. 1

key reaction used to synthesize the target enediynes **33** and **34**. For the the construction of the simple 10-membered azaenediynes **33**, *cis*-dichloroethylene was first monocoupled with homopropargyl alcohol. The resulting 6-chlorohex-5-ene-3-ynol **36** was converted to the azide **38**, which upon reduction with $\text{PPh}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ produced the amine, isolated as the *p*-toluene sulfonamide **39**. Another round of Pd⁰-catalyzed coupling with propargyl *t*-butyldimethylsilyl ether gave the acyclic enediynes **40** which was deprotected to the alcohol **41**. Intramolecular *N*-alkylation of the mesylate **42** using $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{DMF}$ under high dilution proceeded smoothly to produce the 10-membered azaenediynes **33** (Scheme 10). The corresponding benzene-fused enediynes **34** was synthe-

Scheme 10. Reagents and condition : (a) 3-Butyn-1-ol, $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$, *n*-BuNH₂, 80°, (b) MsCl, NEt₃, (c) NaN₃, DME, (d) PPh_3 , H₂O, (e) TsCl, DMAP, (f) propargyl *t*-butyldimethylsilyl ether, $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$, *n*-BuNH₂, 80°, (g) CsF, MeOH, (h) MsCl, NEt₃, (i) K_2CO_3 , DMF.

sized in a similar fashion (Scheme 11). However, in this case the Pd⁰-based coupling had to be carried out in the absence of CuI, addition of which led to extensive oxidative dimerization of the acetylene in our hands. An attempt to prepare a 9-membered analog **35** failed; the initial intermolecular *N*-alkylation product **50** underwent intramolecu-

Scheme 11. Reagents and condition : (a) 3-Butyn-1-ol, $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$, *n*-BuNH₂, 80°, (b) MsCl, NEt₃, (c) NaN₃, DME, (d) PPh_3 , H₂O, (e) TsCl, DMAP, (f) propargyl alcohol $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$, *n*-BuNH₂, 80°, (g) MsCl, NEt₃, (h) K_2CO_3 , DMF.

lar cyclization leading to the 18-membered bisazaenediynes **51** (Scheme 12). Just and Singh^{15a} and König *et al.*^{15b} had previously reported the formation of a similar molecule using different routes.

Scheme 12

Thermal reactivity :

The enediynes **33** was found to be sufficiently stable at ambient temperature to allow us to record its ¹H, ¹³C and correlation spectra. The molecule, however, slowly underwent cycloaromatization (BC) in CDCl₃ at room temperature resulting in the formation of a tetrahydroisoquinoline system **54**¹⁶. The *t*_{1/2} at 23° for such a cyclization was found to be around 72 h (*E*_a ~18 kcal mol⁻¹). The Bergman cyclization could be monitored by keeping a solution of the sample in CDCl₃ at a constant temperature and checking the ¹H NMR at different time points. Interestingly, the characteristic peaks at δ 5.84, 4.09, 3.53 and 2.77 for **33** diminished while new peaks at δ 4.22, 3.33 and 2.91 corresponding to the tetrahydroisoquinoline system appeared. Differential scanning calorimetric (DSC)¹⁷ measurement on **1** in the neat liquid state showed the onset temperature for BC to

Scheme 13

Fig. 2. Interaction of supercoiled DNA with enediyne **33**, *p*-bluescript DNA was incubated for 18 h at 37° with various concentration of **33** in phosphate buffer (pH = 7.8) and analyzed by electrophoresis (1% agarose gel, ethidium bromide stain). Lanes : (1) DNA + phosphate buffer (4°), (2) DNA + enediyne ($14\ \mu\text{M}$), (3) DNA + enediyne **33** ($56\ \mu\text{M}$), (6) DNA kept at 37° .

be around 50° . The benzene fused enediyne **34**, on the other hand, is stable at room temperature. The cyclized product, a benzo-tetrahydroisoquinoline derivative **55**, could be isolated by refluxing a chloroform solution of **34** for 3 days followed by chromatography. The $t_{1/2}$ for the cycloaromatization was found to be ~ 52 h at 65° . The molecule showed an onset temperature for BC of $\sim 110^\circ$ when checked by DSC. Thus, fusion of an aromatic ring on to the 10-membered azaenediyne caused a significant elevation of the activation barrier to cycloaromatization. One would expect that the larger ene bond distance (1.39 Å) possibly led to an increase in the distance between the reacting acetylenic carbons in **34** thereby slowing down the kinetics of BC. However, as indicated earlier, MM2 calculations showed the c,d-distance in **34** to be 3.24 Å, well within Nicolaou's proposed critical range for spontaneous cyclization at room temperature thus possibly ruling out the above proposition. An alternate explanation based on the lower gain of resonance energy in the naphthalene-like TS for the BC of **34** acting as weaker driving force compared to an isolated benzenoid TS for cyclization of **33** seems more plausible.

The spontaneous cycloaromatization of the enediyne **33** prompted us to check its DNA-cleaving activity. Thus **33** was incubated with *p*-bluescript double stranded supercoiled DNA at 37° for 18 h and then run in an agarose gel (0.7%), already stained with ethidium bromide. The gel pattern (Fig. 2) clearly demonstrated the ability of **33** to cleave double bond stranded DNA even in μ molar concentrations.

Pyramidalization of nitrogen atom in a cyclic framework is an important issue for molecules having a cyclic amide group. β -Lactams offer a classic example of such a system where more pyramidal nitrogen usually confers higher chemical as well as biological reactivity¹⁸. We became curious to know what effect the pyramidal character of the ring nitrogen atom has on the kinetics of BC in the monocyclic enediyne. We hoped to achieve the perturbation of the nature of hybridization of the ring nitrogen atom in monocyclic azaenediyne by attaching different aryl sulphonamido

groups on to the nitrogen. The presence of electron-withdrawing group at the 4-position of the aromatic ring should enhance the conjugation between the sulphone and the nitrogen lone-pair thus making the latter less pyramidal with less sp^3 -character compared to that in systems where electron-donating group or simply hydrogen is present at the 4-position. Since less pyramidalization means more planarity and higher electronegativity, the reactivity of such an enediyne towards BC is expected to be higher than that in systems in which the nitrogen has greater pyramidal character. To have an idea about how the distance between the reacting acetylenic carbon atoms depends on the extent of pyramidalization of nitrogen, we have carried out MM2 calculations on azaenediyne **56** and **57** having complete sp^2 or sp^3 nitrogen atom. For better comparison, positive charge is retained in both the systems. Interestingly, the c,d-distance for the iminium enediyne **56** came out to be 3.21 Å, shorter than that for the ammonium enediyne **57** for which the c,d-distance came out to be 3.28 Å (Fig. 3). Also, the two acetylenic bonds in **56** are nearly coplanar while in **57** they are deviated from planarity by an angle of $\sim 5^\circ$. Schmittel and Kiau¹⁹ has recently demonstrated that electron-withdrawing groups attached to the triple bond termini lower the activation energy for cycloaromatization due to decreased steric repulsion between the in-plane π -orbitals. Consideration of all the above aspects would predict higher reactivity for **33b** compared to **33** or **33a**. MM2 calculations, however, failed to reveal any noticeable difference in the conformations of enediyne **33**, **33a** and **33b**.

Initially, the kinetics of BC were recorded by measuring the ratio of the cyclized product (**54/54a/54b**) and the starting enediyne (**33/33a/33b**) from the ^1H NMR taken at different time points. The cyclizations showed first order kinetics. Fig. 4 is graphical representation of the rate of cy-

Fig. 4. Rate of BC, determined from the rate of appearance of starting enediyne (●) **33**, (■) **33a**, (▲) **33b**

clization²⁰ of the enediynes **33/33a/33b**. It appears that the nitro enediyne **33b** with less pyramidal character reacted more slowly compared to enediynes **33** and **33a**. This was unexpected as the less pyramidal nitrogen and less repulsion between the acetylenes in **33a** would make it more planar and consequently, the molecule should have a lower activation barrier. When we repeated the kinetics by recording the disappearance of the starting enediyne (with respect to a known concentration of acetonitrile) with time and the results were plotted (Fig. 5) the situation became reverse. The nitro-enediyne **33b** was disappearing at a faster rate relative to the other two enediynes **33** and **33a** for which the rates of disappearance were almost similar. Assuming that the only reaction via which the concentrations of the enediynes can be lowered is by Bergman cyclization, it can be concluded that **33b**, with less pyramidal nitrogen, was forming the diradical **52b** at a faster rate compared to **33** or

Fig. 5. Rate of BC, determined from the rate of disappearance of starting enediyne (●) **33**, (■) **33a**, (▲) **33b**.

33a. However, the reactivity of **52b** towards abstraction of deuterium from CDCl_3 was less (because of less favorable SOCO-LUMO interaction) compared to the diradicals **52** or **52a**. This may explain why we see less isoquinoline product from **33b** as the diradical **52b** was probably disappearing by other routes (e.g. polymerization).

In conclusion we have demonstrated that 10-membered azaenediynes containing one nitrogen atom can undergo spontaneous BC at room temperature. The kinetics can be perturbed by fusion of an aromatic ring. Also an inverse relationship has been observed between the rate of BC and the extent of pyramidalization of the ring N-atom. This will be important for the design of azaenediynes with better chemical and biological reactivity profile.

Experimental

All the solvents were dried and purified prior to use. Methylene chloride, triethylamine and DMF were distilled from calcium hydride. All reactions were carried out under nitrogen. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 883 spectrophotometer. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 (unless mentioned otherwise) on a Bruker AC 200 spectrometer. M.p.s. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Anhydrous Na_2SO_4 was used for drying organic extracts after reaction workup. DSC measurements were done using a Netzsch 40 instrument.

6-Chlorohex-5-ene-3-yn-ol (36) : To a dry degassed benzene (15 ml), solution of *cis*-dichloroethylene (305 μl , 4 mmol), $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (185 mg, 0.16 mmol) and *n*-butylamine (1.75 ml, 16 mmol) were added and stirred for 5 min under argon. Then CuI (152 mg, 0.8 mmol) was added and stirred for 20 min followed by addition of 3-butyn-1-ol (330 μl , 4.4 mmol). Stirring was continued for 3 h at room temperature. A mixture of EtOAc and saturated NH_4Cl (15 ml each) were added and stirred for further 10 min. The organic layer

was washed with water (3×20 ml), dried and filtered. Evaporation afforded an oil from which **36** was isolated by column chromatography (Si-gel, hexane : EtOAc = 1 : 1) as an orange yellow oil (418 mg, 80%); ν_{\max} (CHCl₃) 3340, 1800, 1340, 1060, 850 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 2.15 (1H, bs, OH), 2.67 (2H, dt, *J* 1.8, 6.0 Hz, CH₂CH₂O), 3.79 (2H, t, *J* 6.0 Hz, CH₂O), 5.88 (1H, dd, *J* 1.8, 7.4 Hz, CHCHCl), 6.35 (1H, d, *J* 7.4 Hz, CHCl); δ_{C} 23.8, 60.7, 76.2, 90.0, 112.0, 127.6; *m/z* (EI) 132, 130 (M⁺); (HRMS : Found M⁺, 130.0186. C₆H₇³⁵ClO requires M⁺ 130.0185, found 130.0185).

6-Chlorohex-5-ene-3-yne-1-methanesulfonate (37) : To a solution of **36** (400 mg, 3.1 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (20 ml), methanesulfonyl chloride (265 μ l, 3.3 mmol) and triethylamine (470 μ l, 3.37 mmol) were added at 0°. The reaction mixture was stirred for 15 min at room temperature, then poured into water and CH₂Cl₂ (50 ml each). The organic layer was washed with water (2×50 ml), dried and then evaporated. The residue on chromatography (Si-gel, hexane : EtOAc = 1 : 1) furnished **37** as a pale brown oil (540 mg, 85%); δ_{H} 2.49 (3H, s, SO₂CH₃), 2.69 (2H, dt, *J* 1.8, 6.0 Hz, CH₂CH₂O), 4.82 (2H, t, *J* 6.0 Hz, CH₂O), 5.89 (1H, dd, *J* 1.8, 7.3 Hz, CHCHCl), 6.36 (1H, d, *J* 7.3 Hz, CHCl); *m/z* (EI) 210, 208 (M⁺); (HRMS : Found M⁺, C₇H₉³⁵ClO₃S requires M⁺ 207.9961).

1-Azido-6-chlorohex-5-ene-3-yne (38) : To a solution of the mesylate **37** (500 mg, 2.4 mmol) in dry DMF (20 ml), NaN₃ (625 mg, 4 mmol) was added and stirred for 4 h at room temperature. The mixture was then partitioned between EtOAc and water (50 ml each). The organic layer was washed with water (3×50 ml), dried, filtered and then evaporated. Compound **38** was isolated by chromatography (Si-gel, hexane : EtOAc = 4 : 1) as a pale brown oil (220 mg, 80%); δ_{H} 2.37 (2H, dt, *J* 2.0, 6.8 Hz, CH₂CH₂N), 3.14 (2H, t, *J* 6.8 Hz, CH₂N), 5.54 (1H, dt, *J* 2.1, 7.4 Hz, CHCHCl), 6.05 (1H, d, *J* 7.4, CHCl); δ_{C} 20.54, 49.53, 94.34, 96.04, 111.76, 127.92; *m/z* (EI) 157, 155 (M⁺); (HRMS : Found M⁺ C₆H₆³⁵CIN₃ 155.0250. C₆H₆³⁵CIN₃ requires M⁺ 155.0250).

1-(4-Methylphenylsulfonamido)-6-chlorohex-5-ene-3-yne (39) : To a solution of the azide **38** (200 mg, 1.28 mmol) in THF (15 ml), PPh₃ (370 mg, 1.4 mmol) and water (200 μ l) were added and stirred at room temperature for 20 h. The reaction mixture was then partitioned between EtOAc and water (50 ml each). The organic layer was dried (Na₂SO₄), filtered and evaporated. The oily residue was dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ (15 ml), then *p*-toluenesulfonyl chloride (267 mg, 1.4 mmol) and DMAP (172 mg, 1.4 mmol) were added. The mixture was stirred for 3 h. After partitioning between CH₂Cl₂ and water (50 ml each), the organic

layer was dried (Na₂SO₄), filtered and evaporated. From the oily residue, compound **39** was isolated pure by chromatography (Si-gel, hexane : EtOAc = 1 : 1) as a pale brown oil (200 mg, 55%); δ_{H} 2.38 (3H, s, tosyl-CH₃), 2.94 (2H, t, *J* 6.6 Hz, CH₂CH₂N), 3.08 (2H, dd, *J* 6.6, 13.2 Hz, CH₂N), 5.46 (1H, bs, NH), 5.74 (1H, dd, *J* 2.0, 5.7 Hz, CHCHCl), 6.27 (1H, d, *J* 7.4 Hz, CHCl), 7.25 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, ArH), 7.72 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, ArH); δ_{C} 20.83, 21.38, 41.56, 76.7, 96.0, 111.89, 126.95, 127.74, 129.58, 137.03, 143.14; *m/z* (EI) 285, 283 (M⁺); (HRMS : Found M⁺, 283.0436. C₁₃H₁₄³⁵ClNO₂S requires M⁺, 283.0435).

1-t-Butyldimethylsilyloxy-9-(4-methylphenylsulfonamido)non-4-ene-2,6-di-diyne (40) : To a degassed solution of the chlorosulfonamide **39** (200 mg, 0.71 mmol) in benzene (10 ml), Pd(PPh₃)₄ (33 mg, 0.0284 mmol) and *n*-BuNH₂ (31 μ l, 2.84 mmol) were added and stirred for 5 min. Then CuI (27 mg, 0.142 mmol) was added and stirred for another 20 min after which *t*-butyldimethylsilylpropargyl ether (140 mg, 0.28 mmol), dissolved in degassed benzene (1 ml) was added. Stirring was continued at 40° for 3 h. EtOAc (20 ml) and saturated NH₄Cl solution (10 ml) were added and the mixture was stirred for further 10 min. The organic layer was washed with water (3×20 ml), dried and evaporated. The title compound **40** was isolated by chromatography (Si-gel, hexane : EtOAc = 4 : 1) and isolated as a pale yellow oil (210 mg, 70%); δ_{H} 0.05 (6H, s, SiMe₂), 0.83 (9H, s, C(Me)₃), 2.36 (3H, s, tosyl-CH₃), 2.42 (2H, t, *J* 6.6 Hz, CH₂CH₂N), 3.06 (2H, dd, *J* 6.6 and 13.6 Hz, CH₂N), 4.46 (2H, s, CH₂O), 5.05 (1H, t, *J* 6.2 Hz, NH), 5.68–5.87 (2H, m, CH=CH), 7.22 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, ArH), 7.69 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, ArH); δ_{C} 5.08, 18.29, 21.05, 21.51, 25.86, 41.58, 52.22, 80.45, 82.21, 93.49, 95.63, 119.13, 119.20, 127.08, 129.60, 137.44, 143.10; *m/z* (EI) 418 (MH⁺); (HRMS : Found M⁺, 418.1874. C₂₂H₃₁NO₃SSi⁺H⁺ requires 418.1872).

9-(4-Methylphenylsulfonamido)non-4-ene-2,6-diyne-1-ol (41) : Cesium fluoride (152 mg, 1 mmol) was added to a solution of **40** (250 mg, 0.92 mmol) in CH₃CN and stirred for 4 h at room temperature. The mixture was then filtered through Si-gel and evaporated. Compound **41** was isolated by chromatography (Si-gel, hexane : EtOAc = 1 : 1) as a pale brown oil (160 mg, 90%); δ_{H} 2.41 (3H, s, tosyl-CH₃), 2.49 (2H, t, *J* 6.6 Hz, CH₂CH₂N), 3.12 (2H, dd, *J* 6.3, 12.2 Hz, CH₂N), 4.49 (2H, s, CH₂OH), 5.80 (3H, m, NH, CH=CH), 7.30 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, ArH), 7.75 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, ArH); δ_{C} 20.96, 21.58, 41.43, 51.19, 80.88, 82.62, 93.93, 95.94, 119.51, 119.63, 127.18, 129.73, 137.21, 143.17; *m/z* (EI) 303 (M⁺); (HRMS : Found 303.0935. C₁₆H₁₇NO₃S M⁺, 303.0930).

1-Methanesulfonato-9-(4-methylphenylsulfonamido)non-4-ene-2,6-diyne (42): To a solution of **41** (150 mg, 0.5 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (10 ml), methanesulfonyl chloride (43 μl , 0.55 mmol) and triethylamine (76 μl , 0.55 mmol) were added and the mixture was stirred for 15 min at room temperature. After partitioning between water and CH_2Cl_2 , the organic layer was dried and evaporated. Compound **42** was isolated by chromatography (Si-gel, hexane : EtOAc = 1 : 1) as an oil (160 mg, 85%); δ_{H} 2.44 (3H, s, tosyl- CH_3), 2.56 (2H, t, J 6.2 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 3.11 (3H, s, SO_2CH_3), 3.17 (2H, m, CH_2N), 5.08 (2H, s, CH_2O), 5.14 (1H, t, J 8.4 Hz, NH), 5.80–5.92 (2H, m, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}$), 7.30 (2H, d, J 8.2 Hz, ArH), 7.76 (2H, d, J 8.2 Hz, ArH); δ_{C} 21.27, 21.59, 38.92, 41.45, 58.19, 80.13, 82.62, 89.50, 95.44, 117.82, 122.27, 127.20, 129.75, 137.36, 143.33; m/z (EI) 381 (M^+); (HRMS : Found M^+ , 381.0709. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_2\text{S}$ requires M^+ 381.0705).

1-(4-Methylphenylsulfonyl)-1-azacyclodec-5-ene-3,7-diyne (33): To a solution of the mesylate **42** (100 mg, 0.26 mmol) in DMF (5 ml), K_2CO_3 (180 mg, 1.32 mmol) was added and stirred for 3 h at room temperature. The mixture was poured into EtOAc (50 ml), the organic layer washed with water (3 \times 50 ml), then dried and evaporated. Compound **33** was isolated by column chromatography (Si-gel, hexane : EtOAc = 2 : 1) as an oil (60 mg, 85%); δ_{H} 2.45 (3H, s, tosyl- CH_3), 2.77 (2H, t, J 5 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 3.53 (2H, t, J 5 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 4.09 (2H, s, CCCH_2N), 5.84 (2H, bs, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}$), 7.30 (2H, d, J 8.1 Hz, ArH), 7.75 (2H, d, J 8.1 Hz, ArH); δ_{C} 21.58, 22.45, 42.16, 51.15, 83.82, 89.53, 94.39, 96.54, 122.18, 124.48, 127.39, 129.75, 136.11, 143.46; m/z (EI, CHCl_3) 321 (MHCl^+), 287 (MH_2^+), 286 (MH^+), 285 (M^+), 155, 130 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2$), 104, 102; (HRMS : Found 285.0828. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2\text{S}$ requires M^+ , 285.0824).

2-Bromo-1-(1-hydroxy-3-butyn-4-yl)benzene (43): *o*-Dibromobenzene (500 μl , 4.2 mmol), homopropargyl alcohol (350 μl , 4.62 mmol) and $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (194 mg, 0.169 mmol) were added to degassed *n*-butylamine (15 ml) and the solution was refluxed for 10 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into EtOAc (50 ml) and the organic layer washed with 0.1 *N* HCl (50 ml), then with water (50 ml) and dried. Evaporation *in vacuo* gave an oil from which **43** was isolated by chromatography (Si-gel, hexane : EtOAc = 1 : 1) as a brown oil (850 mg, 90%); δ_{H} 2.90 (2H, t, J 6.1 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}$), 4.01 (2H, t, J 6.1 Hz, CH_2O), 7.26–7.44 (2H, m, ArH), 7.60 (1H, dd, J 1.8, 7.7 Hz, ArH), 7.73 (1H, dd, J 1.28, 7.9 Hz, ArH); m/z (EI) 226, 224 (M^+); (HRMS : Found M^+ , 223.9840. C_{10}H_9 ^{79}BrO requires M^+ , 223.9837).

2-Bromo-1-(1-methanesulfonato-3-butyn-4-yl)benzene (44): It was prepared from the corresponding alcohol (**43**; 200 mg, 0.89 mmol) following the same procedure as described for the preparation of **37**, and isolated as a pale brown oil (230 mg, 85%); δ_{H} 2.95 (2H, t, J 6.8 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}$), 3.06 (3H, s, SO_2CH_3), 4.42 (2H, t, J 6.8 Hz, CH_2O), 7.14–7.28 (2H, m, ArH), 7.43 (1H, dd, J 1.9, 7.6 Hz, ArH), 7.56 (1H, dd, J 1.4, 9.3 Hz, ArH); m/z (EI) 304, 302 (M^+); (HRMS : Found M^+ , 301.9614. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}$ $^{79}\text{BrO}_3\text{S}$ requires M^+ , 301.9612).

2-Bromo-1-(1-azido-3-butyn-4-yl)benzene (45): It was prepared following the same procedure as described for **38** and isolated as a pale brown oil (78%); δ_{H} 2.76 (2H, t, J 6.9 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 3.51 (2H, t, J 6.9 Hz, CH_2N), 7.08–7.27 (2H, m, ArH), 7.43 (1H, d, J 7.5 Hz, ArH), 7.55 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz, ArH); m/z (EI) 251, 249 (M^+); (HRMS : Found M^+ , 248.9905. C_{10}H_8 $^{79}\text{BrN}_3$ requires M^+ , 248.9902).

2-Bromo-1-[1-(4-methylphenylsulfonamido)-3-butyn-4-yl]benzene (46): It was prepared from the azide **45** (120 mg, 0.48 mmol) via reduction with Ph_3P (126 mg, 0.45 mmol) and water (200 μl) followed by protection with *p*-toluenesulfonyl chloride and Et_3N (1.2 eq. each), (90 mg, 52%); δ_{H} 2.42 (3H, s, tosyl- CH_3), 2.61 (2H, t, J 6.4 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 3.23 (2H, dd, J 6.4, 12.8 Hz, CH_2N), 5.25 (1H, t, J 6.2 Hz, NH), 7.09–7.23 (2H, m, ArH), 7.28 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz, tosyl-H), 7.38 (1H, dd, J 1.4, 7.5 Hz, ArH), 7.55 (1H, dd, J 1.4, 7.8 Hz, ArH), 7.79 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz, tosyl-H); m/z (EI) 379, 377 (M^+) (HRMS : Found M^+ , 377.008. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}$ $^{79}\text{BrNO}_2\text{S}$ requires M^+ , 377.0086).

2-(1-Hydroxyprop-2-yn-1-yl)-1-[4-(4-methylphenylsulfonamido)-3-butyn-4-yl]benzene (47): The bromotosylate **46** (80 mg, 0.22 mmol), dissolved in degassed *n*-butylamine (8 ml), was treated with $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (10 mg, 0.009 mmol) and propargyl alcohol (16 μl , 0.27 mmol). The mixture was refluxed for 20 h, then partitioned between EtOAc and 0.1 *N* HCl (30 ml each). The organic layer was dried over Na_2SO_4 , filtered and evaporated *in vacuo*. The title compound was isolated by column chromatography (Si-gel, hexane : EtOAc = 1 : 1) as an oil (60 mg, 80%); δ_{H} 2.41 (3H, s, tosyl- CH_3), 2.59 (2H, t, J 5.8 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 3.21 (2H, t, J 5.8 Hz, CH_2N), 4.56 (2H, s, CH_2OH), 5.52 (1H, t, J 1.50 Hz, NH), 7.23–7.36 (4H, m, tosyl-H, ArH), 7.44–7.48 (2H, m, ArH), 7.80 (2H, d, J 8.3 Hz, tosyl-H); m/z (EI) 353 (M^+); (HRMS : Found M^+ , 353.1088. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_3\text{S}$ requires M^+ , 353.1086).

2-(1-Methanesulfonatoprop-2-yn-3-yl)-1-[1-(4-methylphenylsulfonamido)-3-butyn-4-yl]benzene (48): It was prepared from the alcohol **47** following the same pro-

cedure as described for **36**, and isolated as a brown oil (85%); δ_{H} 2.40 (3H, s, tosyl-CH₃), 2.63 (2H, t, *J* 5.9 Hz, CH₂CH₂N), 3.10 (3H, s, SO₂CH₃), 3.1[†] (2H, t, *J* 5.9 Hz, CH₂N), 5.17 (2H, s, CH₂O), 5.75 (1H, t, *J* 1.5 Hz, NH), 7.20–7.40 (5H, m, tosyl-H, ArH), 7.43–7.53 (1H, m, ArH), 7.78 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, tosyl-H); *m/z* (EI) 431 (M⁺); (HRMS : Found M⁺, 431.0863. C₂₁H₂₁NO₅S₂ M⁺, 431.0861).

1-[4-Methylphenylsulfonyl]-[5,6]benz-1-azacyclodec-3,7-diyne (34) : The mesylate **48** (50 mg, 0.12 mmol), dissolved in dry DMF (5 ml), was treated with K₂CO₃ (85 mg, 0.61 mmol) and the mixture was stirred for 3 h at room temperature. It was then partitioned between EtOAc and water (50 ml each). The organic layer was washed with water (3×50 ml), dried and evaporated. From the residue, the title compound was isolated by column chromatography as a pale brown oil (30 mg, 80%); δ_{H} 2.40 (3H, s, tosyl-CH₃), 2.80 (2H, t, *J* 5 Hz, CH₂CH₂N), 3.58 (2H, t, *J* 5 Hz, CH₂N), 4.15 (2H, s, NCH₂CC), 7.24–7.29 (6H, m, tosyl-H, ArH), 7.75 (2H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, tosyl-H); *m/z* (EI) 335 (M⁺); (HRMS : Found M⁺, 335.0982. C₂₀H₁₇NO₂S requires M⁺, 335.0981).

1,10-Bis(4-methylphenylsulfonyl)-1,10-bisazacyclooctadec-5,14-diene-3,7,12,16-tetrayne (51) : To a solution of **49** (50 mg, 0.14 mmol) in dry DMF (5 ml), K₂CO₃ (95 mg, 0.68 mmol) was added and the mixture was stirred for 3 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then partitioned between EtOAc and water (50 ml each). The organic layer was washed with water (3×50 ml), dried and evaporated. The residue on chromatography (Si-gel, hexane : EtOAc = 2 : 1 as eluent) furnished **51** as viscous oil (35 mg, 90%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3438, 2925, 1633, 1162, 670 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 2.41 (6H, s, tosyl-CH₃), 4.34 (8H, s, NCH₂), 5.58 (4H, s, CH=CH), 7.29 (4H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, tosyl-H), 7.69 (4H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, tosyl-H); δ_{C} 21.51, 36.85, 83.10, 88.93, 120.25, 127.94, 129.51, 135.10, 143.99; *m/z* (EI) 542 (M⁺); (HRMS : Found M⁺, 542.1339. C₃₀H₂₆N₂O₄S₂ requires M⁺, 542.1335).

1-(Phenylsulphonyl)-1-azacyclodec-5-ene-3,7-diyne (33a) : It was prepared following the procedure as described for **33**, (90%); δ_{H} 2.77 (2H, t, *J* 5.0 Hz, NCH₂CH₂), 3.52 (2H, t, *J* 5.0 Hz, NCH₂CH₂), 4.12 (2H, s, NCH₂C), 5.84 (2H, bs, CH=CH), 7.48–7.58 (3H, m, ArH), 7.83–7.86 (2H, m, ArH).

1-(4-Nitrophenylsulphonyl)-1-azacyclodec-5-ene-3,7-diyne (33b) : It was prepared following the same procedure as described for **33**, (85%); δ_{H} 2.75 (2H, t, *J* 5.01 Hz, N-CH₂CH₂), 3.51 (2H, t, *J* 5.07 Hz, N-CH₂CH₂), 4.23 (2H,

s, N-CH₂-C), 7.23 (4H, s, ArH), 8.07 (2H, d, *J* 8.86 Hz, ArH), 8.29 (2H, d, *J* 8.82 Hz, ArH).

Procedure for rate determination for BC of enediyne 33/33a/33b :

From the ratio product and starting material : The enediyne **33/33a/33b** was dissolved in CDCl₃ (600 μ l) in a NMR tube and kept at 23°. ¹H NMR was recorded at various time points. The ratio of the cyclized product and the remaining starting material was determined from the integrations of the singlets at δ 4.3 (for the cyclized product) and 4.2 (for the starting enediyne).

From the disappearance of the product : To a solution of the enediyne **33/33a/33b** (10 mg) in CDCl₃ in a NMR tube, acetonitrile (2 μ l) was added and the tube sealed. The solution was kept at 23° and the proton spectrum was recorded at various time points. The rate of the disappearance of the starting enediyne was calculated from the ratio of integrations of the singlets at δ 4.2 (for H-2 for the starting enediyne) and at 1.98 (acetonitrile methyl).

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20. Rate of cyclization was expressed as $\ln[(a-x)/a]$, where a is the initial concentration of the enediyne, and x the concentration of the cyclized product at different time points.